

Gender bias in AI and everywhere else

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Abstract

This is a preliminary literature review for gender bias in AI, data science and in society. It has been done for the report of the AI4LABOUR project (<https://ai4labour.com/>).

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1 Gender bias everywhere: it is not just about numbers

“Where have all the women gone?” and “Why do women leave science and engineering?” are the titles of two articles published in 2007 and 2016 (Mitchell, 2007; Hunt, 2016). These are two of many works published over the past decades to find the reasons why women are leaving science and engineering jobs (Rosser & Taylor, 2008; Koenig, 2020; Pantel, 2020). Today, we are still asking ourselves these questions, and have unfortunately normalised that women in computing and science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) leave their jobs and only represent less than 24% of the total workforce of STEM (Pantel, 2020).

We could also ask ourselves “where has the intelligence gone?”. AI is a term that has been misused in the past years, most of the times AI-related technologies do not imply any form of intelligence. The goal of artificial intelligence (AI) is to reproduce and formalise aspects of intelligence in humans and in nature by using computational and mathematical paradigms. But trying to reproduce or modelling aspects of intelligence does not mean that the systems designed will be equipped with intelligence. Indeed, currently, there is much debate on stopping the use of ‘intelligence’ and stopping the AI hype. Data science, which may use some techniques from the field of artificial intelligence, comprises any form of computation which involves data, and it is much more than statistics. In this review, we will use AI as a general term that includes the use of computer science and engineering tools to automate some tasks in industry, our jobs and our day-to-day lives. We will put special attention to STEM careers since they are the workforce behind what is currently called AI.

Numbers are clear: less than 20% of technical workers in companies are women (Buolamwini & Hedayat, 2019) and only 22% of professionals working in AI around the world are female (Bello, Blowers, Schneegans, & Straza, 2021). The numbers are dramatic if we add other attributes, like race and disadvantaged backgrounds, for example, less than 2% of the workforce in technology are women of colour (Buolamwini & Hedayat, 2019). Moreover, women working in STEM fields are 45% more likely than men to leave within the year (Porter, 2014). We have been talking over and over again about the problem for decades without finding a solution. Bias against women in male-dominated work environments is undeniable, especially in computer science and engineering. Currently, biases are masked within biases in algorithms. Algorithms and data are just a reflection of what we are as humans and what the sector is. Most of the techniques under the umbrella of what is nowadays called AI are data-driven techniques, which are just a small part of what AI is. This review focuses on data-driven AI tools, that is, techniques based on the acquisition, collection, classification and analysis of big amounts of data. Before analysing bias in algorithms, we must analyse the workplace reality and culture in the areas of computing, engineering and AI-based careers.

2 The culture and reality in AI-based environments

Whilst there is a lot of effort to attract “more girls” to study computer science and information technologies (IT) degrees – with cautiously good recent results (British Computer Society (BCS), 2022) –, more women are leaving science, technology and engineering jobs. Women are leaving not due to lack of motivation, they leave due to bias in evaluations, lack of sponsors, lack of mentors and a sense of isolation (Porter, 2014). Women in STEM receive less money for research from public funding bodies. They get less promotion and less mentoring and support. They often receive less salaries than their male colleagues carrying out the same role, although in many cases they are more competent and have more merits and expertise. They are less in number (Nelson, 2014; Navarro-López, 2014, 2022; Pantel, 2020; Bello et al., 2021). The shocking thing is that despite these facts, the community is still asking themselves why women are leaving science and engineering, both in academia and industry. Another ‘Women in’ event will make no difference, due to the widespread tokenism, privilege, abuse and discrimination against women in academia, science and technology (Navarro-López, 2014, 2022; E.M. Navarro-López, M. Díaz, E. García-Canseco, Y. Wilson, 2021; Trades Union Congress & Everyday Sexism Project, 2016; Clancy, Nelson, Rutherford, & Hinde, 2014; Moss-Racusina, Dovidio, Brescoll, Graham, & Handelsman, 2012; Handley, Brown, Moss-Racusin, & Smith, 2015). In sum, women leave STEM jobs and academia due to an unsympathetic, hostile and toxic workplace culture (Pantel, 2020).

The increase of the number of women in STEM is important, however, the most important action is to change the system so that toxic work practices are not also adopted and perpetuated by women. The benefits are clear: it has been shown that more diverse departments are more efficient, productive and creative (Nelson, 2014).

3 Bullying, harassment and sexual harassment

Bullying and harassment is a major problem to add to the list of problems mentioned above. Harassment is not new in male-dominated workplaces. All types of harassment, especially sexual harassment, have been reported since the 19th century (Bularzik, 1978). Today, in the 21st century, more than half (52%) of women, and nearly two-thirds (63%) of women aged 18–24 years old, said they have experienced sexual harassment at work (Trades Union Congress & Everyday Sexism Project, 2016). These figures correspond to reported cases, however, there might be many more, since silence of the victims of abuse and violence at workplaces is one of the main problems. Silence is a consequence of inadequate responses from institutions that tend to protect the majority group perpetrating abuse (Trades Union Congress & Everyday Sexism Project, 2016).

As it was mentioned in the previous section, bullying and harassment are at the backbone of male-dominated STEM workplaces, especially in competitive and toxic environments like academia (Clancy et al., 2014; Navarro-López, 2022). We wonder if AI systems will also mimic the bullying and harassment implicit in the technological environment they were developed. It is a positive step to build chatbots to combat bullying and harassment in social platforms; recently, these chatbots have been used to help track bullying and harassment at work (Olson, 2018). AI can be used to monitor offensive messages as well as potential sexual harassment or online bullying, including bullying and harassment at the workplace (Huet, 2022). There is still work to be done to ensure that these algorithms do not present biases.

4 Gender bias in algorithms and data feminism

Under the scenario presented above, it is clear that algorithms, particularly data-driven algorithms – designed by humans –, will reflect gender and racial biases with clear discrimination against women and other underrepresented communities. Data fed into algorithms are biased as the male-dominated fields of computer science, artificial intelligence and machine learning are (Leavy, 2018; Díaz, 2022; Criado-Perez, 2019; Gray, 2022). This is reflected in different recent studies: from computational linguistics and natural language processing to advertising ((Thelwall, 2018) and references therein); from facial recognition (Buolamwini, 2022) to automated recruiting and selection tools (Bogen, 2019; N. Martínez et al., 2021); from misdiagnosis in medicine (D. Cirillo et al., 2020; Davis, 2021; Albert & Delano, 2022; Criado-Perez, 2019) to credit rating (Kelly & Mirpourian, 2021) and internet search algorithms (Vlasceanua & Amodio, 2022).

Over the past years, the term “data feminism” (D’Ignazio & Klein, 2020) has emerged as a necessary counter movement to the current status quo (O’Neil, 2017). Some studies highlight how “AI is becoming a more powerful force capable of perpetrating global violence through three epistemic processes: datafication (extraction and dispossession), algorithmisation (mediation and governmentality) and automation (violence, inequality and displacement of responsibility)” (Ricaurte, 2022). New paradigms are sought to have “ethical machines” and algorithms that can be unbiased, transparent and respectful (Blackman, 2022), with the genuine goal of improving the human-built environment in STEM and society. But there is still a long way to have unbiased algorithms, as there is a long way to have an unbiased society.

Algorithms and AI-based systems can amplify racism, sexism, classism, and other forms of discrimination that already exist in our societies (Buolamwini, 2022). Recently, there is an increasing number of works reporting the harm that algorithms can do in societies. Particularly, with facial recognition systems that cannot identify dark-skinned faces accurately (Buolamwini, 2018; S. Kantayya (Director), 2020). The terms “coded gaze” (Buolamwini, 2022) and “coded bias” (S. Kantayya (Director), 2020) have been coined. If the technology is produced by only 20% of women and with barely 2% of people of colour, algorithms will reflect this imbalance and discrimination (Fefegha, 2021). This is why it is essential to have transparency in how systems are trained, which data have been used to train the systems and where their limitations are:

that is, transparency is needed in the design, implementation and deployment of algorithmic systems. As Dr. Buolamwini states “if you are not intentional about being inclusive, what you will do is perpetuating exclusion” (Buolamwini & Hedayat, 2019). She has strongly pushed algorithmic justice via the “Algorithmic Justice League”, a movement towards equitable and accountable AI (<https://www.ajl.org/>).

5 Gender bias in AI at work

There are three main aspects to consider in relation to gender bias in the near future job automation and AI-based algorithms applied to different work-related processes:

- **Women are predicted to lose more jobs in the future.** As the recent UNESCO report establishes, the digital revolution to be intelligent must be inclusive (Bello et al., 2021). Data are not very optimistic:
 1. Women are at more risk to miss out on the jobs of the future. United Nations predicts that women will lose 5 jobs for each job they will gain within the Industry 4.0, in contrast, men will lose 3 jobs per each job they will gain (Bello et al., 2021).
 2. The digitalisation and the future of work establish the dominant role of men in the development of technology, and this may dramatically impact the future of work (European Institute for Gender Equality, 2020).
- **Gender bias in automated work-related processes.** As it was mentioned in previous sections, algorithms used in hiring process, interviews, promotions and performance analysis present a clear gender bias (Huet, 2022). On the positive side, there are recent efforts to design AI systems to revert the gender bias at work. This is the example of the *Startup Pipeline Equity*, which has the goal of helping make decisions about hiring, pay, performance, potential and promotion free of bias (if this is ever possible) (Ajao, 2021).
- **Hidden, unpaid and invisible work behind software and AI systems development.** There is an increasing number of invisible and unpaid work in the development of AI systems (Toxtli, Suri, & Savage, 2021; Gahntz, 2018). It is necessary to analyse if this situation is worse for women and other disadvantaged communities.

6 Inclusion of disadvantaged backgrounds

More women and underrepresented communities are needed in STEM and AI-based jobs, but the aim should not be to substitute privileged men by privileged women. Everybody must be included. AI is typically run by privileged communities, especially in academia where there is bias against disadvantaged backgrounds (Morgan et al., 2022).

It is enlightening to see how there are recent efforts from the AI community: on the one hand, to design algorithms taking into consideration the needs and ways of life of indigenous people (Indigenous Protocol and Artificial Intelligence Working Group, J.E. Lewis (editor), 2020), and on the other hand, to use AI systems to empower women in rural communities (Sultana, Sengers, & Dell, 2018). It is also remarkable the increasing number of movements like the “Algorithmic Justice League” or “People of Color in Tech” (POCIT) (Buolamwini, 2022, 2018; Buolamwini & Hedayat, 2019; S. Kantayya (Director), 2020; Fefegha, 2021) to raise awareness of the historic and still present discrimination against people of colour in AI systems outputs as well as in society.

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